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IMPROVING THE MECHANISMS OF PREPARING 5TH-7TH GRADE STUDENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE BASED ON EDUCATIONAL APPROACHES

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Annotation: This article examines the issues of improving the content and mechanisms of preparing 5th -7th grade students for family life based on educational approaches. Considering the psychological and social characteristics of adolescence, effective ways of developing family values, responsibility, mutual respect and communication skills in students are analyzed. The importance of strengthening cooperation between school and family as well as the use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods is also discussed. The article provides practical recommendations aimed at improving the effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: education, family, student, family life, pedagogical approach, values, cooperation, interactive methods.

Introduction. Today, in the education system, the issue of not only increasing students' knowledge levels but also preparing them for life is becoming increasingly relevant. In particular 5th – 7th grade pupils are entering the adolescent period, during which their social relationships, personal views and values system begin to take shape. Guiding them correctly during this period forms one of the important foundations of the process of preparing for future family life. In this process, it is necessary to develop qualities such as responsibility, respect and communication culture in students based on the cooperation of family, school and society. However, despite this, it is observed that work in this direction is not always carried out systematically in practice. Therefore, improving the mechanisms of preparing 5th – 7th grade pupils for family life, applying modern pedagogical approaches, and implementing effective methods is one of the important tasks of the current educational process. Furthermore, in today's globalization process, young people's rapid access to information flow significantly impacts their worldview and value systems. For this reason, forming correct life perspectives in pupils and developing sense of respect and responsibility towards family relationships becomes even more relevant. The educational influences provided to children during the school education process must be inextricably linked with the family environment. Because the family is the child's first social environment and the values formed there directly influence their future life decisions. From this perspective, strengthening the cooperation between school and family increases the effectiveness of the process of preparing pupils for family life.

Literature review. The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On education” (2020). This law establishes that the main goal of education is the formation of a well-rounded individual. The document emphasizes that it is important for children not only to acquire knowledge but also to acquire life skills and educational qualities. This serves as a legal basis for preparing 5th-7th grade students for family life. The national program for personal training of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This program identifies preparing the individual for social life and strengthening cooperation between family and educational institutions as one of the main directions. It particularly emphasizes the continuity of the education and upbringing process. This document is a crucial conceptual basis for preparing children for future family and social life.

John Bowlby- Attachment and loss. According to Bowlby’s attachment theory, early emotional relationships between a child and parents strongly influence later social and family relationships. He argues that a secure environment in childhood ensures stable psychological development of the individual. This theory serves as an important psychological basis for forming family values in 5th-7th grade pupils.

Lev Vygotsky- Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes. Vygotsky’s socio-cultural development theory shows that a child’s development occurs through communication and social environment. He introduced the concept of the “zone of proximal development”, arguing that with the help of adults and peers a child acquires new skills. This approach demonstrates the importance of social education in preparing students for family life.

Jean Piaget- the psychology of the child . Piaget studied the stages of children’s cognitive development, emphasizing that logical thinking and abstract concepts form during adolescence. He scientifically substantiates that expanding life and family concepts to students during this period is effective.

D.B. Elkonin – Psychology of Play / Developmental Psychology of Adolescence. Elkonin views adolescence as a stage of social and emotional development of the personality. He emphasizes the importance of relationships with peers and social roles during this period. That is, he shows the necessity of a psychological approach in preparing 5th-7th grade students for family life during this period [6].

Research Methodology. This research focused on studying the mechanisms of preparing 5th-7th grade students for family life based on educational approaches, carried out in the harmony of theoretical and practical approaches. The object of the research was determined as the educational process of 5th-7th grade students in general secondary schools.

The process of forming readiness for family life in children was analyzed considering their age and psychological characteristics. 5th-7th grade pupils are in the initial stage of adolescence, during which their desire for independence, emotional volatility and interest in peers’ approaches based on explanation, role modeling and practical activity of rather than authoritarianism, are important. In the research, the concept of preparation for family life was considered as a process of forming in children’s perceptions future family roles (parent, child, spouse) developing responsibility,

communication culture, and family values several types of educational approaches were taken as a basis in the research, including: moral approach (forming respect, honest and responsibility), social approach (adapting to societal relationships), psychological approach (emotional stability and communication culture) and activity-based approach (role-playing games and analyses of life situation). The following scientific-methodical methods were used during the research: theoretical analyses, pedagogical observation interview, questionnaire, as well as methods of analyzing and summarizing the obtained results. The effectiveness of interactive methods such as role playing games, case studies group discussions and class hours was also studied in the practical process. Based on the obtained empirical approaches play and an important role in the progress of preparing 5th-7th grade pupils for family life and scientific conclusion were developed to improve direction the subject of the research consists of the educational approaches used in preparing these children for family life in the mechanisms for improving them the following scientific methodical methods were used in the research: theoretical analysis, pedagogical observation interview questionnaire as well as methods of analyzing and summarizing the obtained results. During theoretical analysis, scientific literature related to the topic, pedagogical and psychological sources and regulatory legal documents were studied. During pedagogical observation pupils behavior during lessons, their mutual relationships and their activity in educational events were analyzed. Through interview method the opinions of teachers and class teachers were studied and through the questionnaire, pupils attitudes towards family values, responsibility and communication culture were determined. The obtained empirical data were systematized based on the research results scientifically grounded conclusions were developed to improve the mechanisms of preparing 5th-7th grade pupils for family life. **Conclusion recommendations.** Based on the research results, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. Development and implementation of special educational programs for preparing 5th-7th grade pupils for family life.
2. Organising regular seminars and trainings for parents to strengthen school-family cooperation.
3. Widespread use of interactive methods (role-playing games, analysis of life situation) in the educational process.
4. Establishing psychological sessions aimed at developing family values responsibility and communication culture and children.
5. Organizing professional development courses to enhance the methodical knowledge of class teachers and subject teachers in this direction

According to the research results it was determined that the process of preparing 5th-7th grade pupils for family life is one of the important directions of the education and upbringing system. During this age period, as pupils personal views, moral values and social relationships are formed, educational approaches gain particular importance. Analysis and observations showed that when school-family

cooperation is sufficiently, respect communication culture and values. However, the fact that this process is not always organized systematically and continuously in practice leads to care time shortcomings. Therefore, there is a need to improve the mechanisms preparing 5th-7th grade pupils for family life and in this process using modern pedagogical approaches and interactive methods is of great importance.

In conclusion, it was determined that the process of 5th-7th grade pupils for family life is one of the important stages in the social moral and psychological development of an individual. The values attitudes and life perspectives formed in pupils during this ages directly influence their future family life. Based on the analyses it can be said that the educational process organized on the basis of educational approaches is effective in forming a positive attitude towards responsibility, respect, communication culture and family values in pupils. Especially in an environment with strong school family cooperation, the effectiveness of educational influence increase significantly. It was determined that there are certain shortcomings in practice in this direction, meaning that educational work is not always carried out systematically and continuously. This can affect the level of students' readiness for family life to a certain extent. In general, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms of preparing 5th-7th grade students for family life, and in this process, it is important to effectively use modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, and psychological approaches.

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